

ENZYMATIC TRANSESTERIFICATION OF LIPASES OBTAINED FROM BACTERIAL AND PLANT SOURCES

¹Gayatri Nahak, ²Chandra Kanti Mohanty, ²N.K. Mohapatra and ¹R.K. Sahu
¹B.J.B. Autonomous College, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, ²Academy of Management and Information Technology, Khorda, Orissa

ABSTRACT

The use of vegetable oil as a fuel source in diesel engine is as old as the diesel engine itself. However, the demand to develop and utilize plant oils and animal fats as biodiesel fuels has been limited recently. The technical definition of biodiesel is “The mono alkyl ester of long fatty acids derived from renewable lipid feedstock such as vegetable oils or animal fats, for use in compression ignition (diesel) engines” (National Biodiesel Board, 1996). It is one of the many alternative fuel options that can help in oil dependence. Non-edible oils like *Jatropha curcas*, *Ricinus communis*, *Calophyllum inophyllum* etc can be used for the production of biodiesel. With regard to protein/lipase content of the different sources as has been found out, highest protein content was found to be in *Calophyllum* seed followed by *J. curcas* per gm. of source material. However gross estimate represents the soluble protein of which the activity screening further justifies the use of enzyme extract from *Xanthomonas* Spp as lipase source for transesterification in a cost effective way. The protocol followed is simple without involvement of much technical complication may be further looked into to standardize a general acceptable method. The bacterial lipase and lipase from *Jatropha curcas* appear to have highest efficiency in transesterifying *Jatropha* oil as enzyme used is partially pure. The ester yield is as high 80-85%, can be considered for further research to increase the production keeping the cost of process at lowest minimum. There was no scope to go for kinetic study of enzyme from individual sources along with assessment of quality of ester, therefore it is premature to comment on standardized protocol and experimentally designed to highlight the scale up.

KEYWORDS: Biodiesel, Enzymatic transesterification, Lipase, Immobilized enzyme, Ester.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiesel is a renewable fuel that can be synthesized from edible, non-edible and waste oils. Due to diminishing petroleum reserves, vegetable oils have attracted attention as a potential renewable source for the production of alternatives to petroleum based fuel. A number of processes have been developed for biodiesel production involving chemical or enzyme catalysis or supercritical alcohol treatment (Fukuda *et al.*, 2001; Warabi *et al.*, 2004). Enzymatic transesterification of triglycerides is a good alternative to chemical process due to its eco-friendly, selective nature and low temperature requirements (Kaieda *et al.*, 1999; Du *et al.*, 2005). Many starting materials such as soybean oil (Schwab *et al.*, 1988; Samukawa *et al.*, 2000), sunflower oil (Belafi Bako *et al.*, 2002; Dossat *et al.*, 2002), cotton seed oil (Oznur *et al.*, 2002), rapeseed oil (Nelson *et al.*, 1996), palm oil (Abigor *et al.*, 2000; Crabbe *et al.*, 2001) and restaurant kitchen wastes (Hsu *et al.*, 2002) have been evaluated for preparation of biodiesel by the enzymatic route. In many countries, like India, where edible oils are not in surplus supply, there is a need to search for alternative starting materials, such as from non-edible oils. Oil of *Jatropha curcas* (Euphobiaceae), non-edible oil, has been chosen for the present investigation. The oil content of *Jatropha* seed ranges from 30 to 50% by weight, whereas in kernel the oil content ranges from 45 to 60%. The fatty acid composition of *Jatropha* oil consists of oleic acid 43.1%, linoleic acid 34.3%, stearic acid 6.9%, palmitic acid 4.2% and other acids 1.4%. *Jatropha curcas* is a low-growing tree, generally planted as a hedge for protecting crops from animals. It can be grown on barren land under harsh conditions and can be cultivated as a part of the strategy for reclaiming degraded lands. Keeping all this in view, the Indian Government has announced a “National Mission on Biodiesel” for *Jatropha* plantation in wasteland regions is to be implemented on an area of 400,000 ha over the next five years (Francis *et al.*, 2005).

There are many reports on biodiesel production using enzyme catalysis by free or immobilized lipases (Kamini *et al.*, 2001; Du *et al.*, 2004; Schwab *et al.*, 1988; Nelson *et al.*, 1996; Hsu *et al.*, 2002 and Shimada *et al.*, 1999; Watanabe *et al.*, 2000). Immobilized lipase in particular recovery from the reaction mixture. There are two major limitations of lipase-catalyzed biodiesel synthesis. One is higher cost (which can be reduced up to a certain extent by immobilization) and another is its inactivation by methanol and glycerol. It has been reported that as methanol is insoluble in vegetable oils, it inhibits the immobilized lipases and thereby decreases the catalytic activity of the transesterification reaction. Further, the hydrophilic by-product glycerol is also insoluble in oil, so it is easily adsorbed onto the surface of the immobilized lipase leading to a negative effect on lipase activity and operational stability. (Shimada *et al.*, 2002). Use of several solvents such as n-hexane and petroleum persisted since the reaction medium has been reported (Ghamuia *et al.*, 2004) but the problem persisted since the inhibition of lipase still occurred due to poor solubility of methanol and glycerol in hydrophobic solvents (Dossat *et al.*, 1999). There are some reports on enhanced biodiesel synthesis in the presence of t-butanol as a solvent (Li *et al.*, 2006; Shah *et al.*, 2004). As both methanol and glycerol are soluble in t-butanol, the inhibitory effect of methanol and glycerol on lipase activity is reduced. Moreover, t-butanol is not a substrate for the lipase because it does not act on tertiary alcohols.

Several micro-organisms that produce solvent-tolerant lipases, either 1,3-specific from *Fusarium* spp. (Shimada *et al.*, 1993) or non-specific from *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* spp. (Sugihara *et al.*, 1992; Ogino *et al.*, 1999), have been reported. Shimada *et al.*, 1999 reported continuous conversion of vegetable oils to methyl esters using lipase in organic. Solvent-free environment. They reported that immobilized *Candida antarctica* lipase was found to be the most effective for the methanolysis among lipases tested. Using same lipase as described above Watanabe *et al.*, developed also continuous production of methyl esters from vegetable oils in three step methanolysis. A mixture of vegetable oil and 1:3 molar equivalent of methanol were fed into the first column that immobilized *Candida antarctica* lipase. Abigor *et al.*, 2000 reported that lipase catalyzed production of alkyl esters by transesterification of palm kernel and coconut oil with different alcohols using PS30 (*Pseudomonas cepacia*) lipase as a catalyst. Biodiesel synthesis from *Jatropha* oil has been reported by *Chromobacterium viscosum* and *Pseudomonas cepacia* lipases. In both the cases the ethanolysis of *Jatropha* oil for biodiesel synthesis has been carried out (Shah and Gupta, 2007; Shah *et al.*, 2004). Immobilized *P. cepacia* lipase was used for the transesterification of soybean oil with methanol and ethanol (Noureddini *et al.*, 2005). Fattyacid ethyl esters have also been prepared from castor oil using-hexane as solvent and two commercial lipases, Novozyme 43 and Liposome IM, as catalysts (De Oliveira *et al.*, 2004). Novozyme 435 have also been used to catalyze the transesterification of crude soybean oils for biodiesel production in a solvent-free medium (Du *et al.*, 2004). Simple alkyl ester derivatives of restaurant grease were prepared using immobilized lipases from *Thermomyces lanuginose* and *C. antarctica*, as biocatalysts (Hsu *et al.*, 2002). Fatty acids esters were reproduced from two Nigerian lauric oils, palm kernel oil and coconut oil, by transesterification of the oils with different alcohols using PS30 lipase as a catalyst. In the conversion of palm kernel oil to alkyl esters (biodiesel), ethanol gave the highest conversion of 72%. Some of the fuel properties compared favorably with international biodiesel specifications (Abigor *et al.*, 2000). Despite its importance, studies on the mechanisms of production of microbial lipases and the role of lipidic substances used as inducers in lipase production are scarce (Shimada *et al.*, 1992). Lipases represent an extremely versatile group of bacterial extracellular enzymes that are capable of performing a variety of important reactions, thereby presenting a fascinating field for future research (Jaeger *et al.*, 1994). The understanding of structure–function relationships will enable researchers to tailor new lipases for biotechnological applications (Jaeger *et al.*, 1999).

At the drop of the works already undertaken in said direction the present work aims at screening of different sources of lipase preferably from plants like *Jatropha curcus*, *Ricinus*, and *Callophylum* and then compared with one species of bacteria like *Xanthomonas* species in three different aspects such as lipase content in terms of soluble protein, enzyme activity and efficiency of transesterification of *Jatropha* oil. Germinated seeds for optimal lipase activity/the screening of the sources is essential to augment further studies on enzymatic transesterification to evolve a suitable strategy with a view to economizing a standard protocol. Moreover the transesterification of *Jatropha* oil with the enzyme extract from the above sources both in free and immobilized form in an ideal reaction environment reported earlier.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

The seeds of *Jatropha curcas*, *Ricinus communis*, *Calophyllum inophyllum*, were collected from Department of Forestry, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology (OUAT), Bhubaneswar, Orissa

Bacterial organisms

The bacterial culture *Xanthomonas* species was collected from the Department of Microbiology, OUAT, Bhubaneswar, Orissa and then they were grown for pure culture in the basal medium for further use.

Chemical and Reagents

Petroleum ether(40-60°C), 1% phenolphthalein, 95% ethanol, 0.1N potassium hydroxide, 0.5N HCl, KOH, Silica gel, CaCl₂, Benzene, Phosphate buffer (pH 7.3) 50mM, Sodium taurocholate (Bile salt), Acetone, Ammonium sulphate, Sodium alginate, Calcium chloride, 50% H₂SO₄, Nutrient broth, glucose, Sterilize sand and double distilled water.

Instrumentations

Soxhlet apparatus, Rotary shaker, Cooling Centrifuge, UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Incubator, Hot-air oven, Laminar-air flow, Separating funnel and mortar and pestle.

Seed germination

The seeds of *J. curcas* and *Ricinus*, *Calophyllum* were thoroughly washed with tap water followed by distilled water. Then they were taken in Petri dishes and kept for germination for 1-2 days for further use.

Bacterial culture

All glass wares were cleaned by soaking in dichromate and sulfuric acid for not less than 24 hours, washing in tap water, and rinsing in distilled water. Then the basal medium was prepared. In practice, the inorganic components were dissolved in about half the necessary volume of water, supplemented by test nutrients if any, made up to volume, distributed in flasks, and autoclaved. Sterile glucose was then added aseptically in the form of a 25 or 50 per cent solution prepared by treating glucose solutions twice at pH 3.0 with norit charcoal, filtering each time with the aid of super-cel, and autoclaving the resulting solution (Hutner, 1944). Series of these media were inoculated under the laminar-air flow chamber uniformly with *Xanthomonas* isolates, which are able to grow in the basal medium, and, after incubation at 37 °C in an incubator it gets its turbidities.

Free enzyme Preparation

Preparation of Acetone powder

The germinated seeds were homogenized in mortar and pestle with cold petroleum ether. Then it was centrifuged successively with ether mixture and then finally ground with cold acetone to fine powder and air dried and preserved at -4°C. The enzyme was extracted from acetone powder by phosphate buffer (pH 7.3). Then they were centrifuged at 1500g for 10min at -4°C. The supernatant was preserved for further analysis and the residue was discarded.

The Nutrient broth containing bacterial species was centrifuged and the bacterial pellet was taken in a mortar and pestle. Then the cells were disrupted using sterile sand as abrasive. Again it was centrifuged and the pellet containing the enzyme was collected and kept at -4°C in a refrigerator for further use during the course of study.

Extraction and Purification of Enzymes

The enzyme was extracted from Acetone powder by phosphate buffer (pH 7.3) and in case of bacterial source the extraction was done by masticating the bacterial cells or pellets in phosphate buffer with sterilized sand or abrasive. The materials were then centrifuged at 1500g for 10 minutes at -4°C. The supernatant was preserved for further analysis and the residue was discarded.

The crude enzyme extract was partially purified by salting out method using 70% ammonium sulfate. The precipitated proteins from all samples were recovered after discarding the supernatant. The precipitate was redissolved in phosphate buffer (50mM) pH 7.3 and dialyzed to make it free from ammonium sulfate. The dialyzed samples were taken as enzyme source.

Assay of Lipase from Acetone Powder

The prepared acetone powder (2gm.) was slightly ground with mortar and pestle with buffer solution (30% KOH+ 50% KH₂PO₄+ 20ml ice cold H₂O). Then it was centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 15 minutes. The pellet was discarded and the supernatant was used as enzyme source (Sadasivam and Manickam., 2008). Same procedure was followed for *Xanthomonas* species.

To 20ml. of substrate 5ml. of phosphate buffer was added and the contents were stirred slowly by keeping the beaker on top of a magnetic stirrer-hot plate maintaining the temperature at 35°C and pH 7.0. 0.5ml. of enzyme was added and the pH was recorded immediately at zero time with timer on (pH at zero time). At regular intervals (10 min) or as the pH drops by about 0.2 units 0.1N NaOH was added to bring the pH back to the original level. This titration was repeated for 30-60 minutes and the volume of NaOH consumed was noted to estimate the protein content in the enzyme sample.

Calculation

The enzyme activity as the amount of enzyme required to release one milliequivalent of free fatty acid/ min./gm. sample and specific activity as milliequivalent/ min./ mg. protein.

$$\text{Enz. Activity (meq./min./gm. Sample)} = \frac{\text{Vol. of the alkali consumed} \times \text{Normality of alkali}}{\text{Wt. of the sample} \times \text{Time (min)}}$$

Screening of Efficiency of Lipase from Different Sources in Transesterification

Immobilization of Enzymes

3g of Sodium alginate was taken in 100ml distilled water and was properly mixed to make a 3% solution. Approximately 0.015g of lipase enzyme was mixed with 10ml of 3% sodium alginate solution. An excess (100ml) of CaCl₂ (0.2M) was stirred by placing the beaker on a magnetic stirrer. Then lipase alginate mixture was added drop wise manner through a pipette into the stirred calcium chloride solution. This resulted in formation of spherical beads of get immobilized enzyme. Then these beads were stored at 5°C for further use.

Enzymatic Transesterification

The enzymatic transesterification was done followed by the method *Jatropha* oil (10gm) and ethanols (2gm) were taken in the ratio of 1:4 (mole ml⁻¹) in a 100 ml conical flask. To this mixture different concentrations of enzymes showing different activity of enzymes in terms of milliequivalent/min/mg protein were taken in solution form were added and stirred. Then heated to 40°C with constant shaking at 200 rpm. Then the samples were withdrawn and analyzed for maximum conversion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transesterification by using Free Enzymes from different sources

From Table-1 the lipase content of *Callophylum* per gm of material is highest with 0.353gms. Followed by germinated seed of *Jatropha* with 0.181gms. the enzyme activity was determined in milliequivalent/min/mg of protein. Assay of the enzyme was conducted with 15 min. time interval of fat hydrolysis and it is clear from the data from Table-2 is that the highest activity was observed in case of *Xanthomonas* sp. Followed by seeds of *Callophylum* with activities of 0.008 milliequivalent and 0.003 milliequivalent.

Comparing the Table-1 and Table-2 it is interesting to observe although *Callophylum* has higher lipase content, activity wise the bacterial sources top the list followed by *Jatropha* seeds having low lipase content keeping aside the *Xanthomonas*, the three other plant sources have varied degree of their efficiencies with high efficiency to be found is *Jatropha* seeds probably due to compatibility of the enzyme with the *Jatropha* oil being originated from same source. The efficiency of enzymes from all the given sources in transesterifying *J. curcas* was too arrived at a comparative assessment in terms of gms. of biodiesel produced using equal concentration of ethanol with varying enzymatic activity level. The optimum level of ethanol concentration for the maximum synthesis of biodiesel was investigated. As was expected, an increase in the number of moles of alcohol with respect to the triglycerides resulted in an increase in the production of esters. Ultimately, the formation of esters reached a maximum level with 1:4 *Jatropha* oil:methanol molar ratio, and a further increase in alcohol concentration resulted in a decrease in the

formation of esters. The maximum biodiesel synthesis rates from rapeseed oil and cotton oil were reported at 1:3:6 and 1:4 oil: methanol ratio, respectively (Li *et al.*, 2006; Royon *et al.*, 2007). The other constituents produced as byproducts in gms. has also been taken into consideration. The reaction environment was maintained at 40°C with reaction time which was happened to be optimum reaction condition as reported earlier. The data of different sources are showing in Table-3, 4, 5, and 6. The effect of enzyme concentration on the transesterification was also investigated. The enzyme concentration was varied in both the case i.e. in free and immobilized forms from 2.5 to 4.5 gm equivalent of material as shown in figure-3, 4, 5, and 6 in free enzyme and Figure-8, 9, 10 and 11. The synthesis of fatty acid initially increased within the enzyme content with maximum conversion rate 90% in case of free enzyme and 90.2% in case of Immobilized form as shown in Table-11 and Figure-7. A previous study has demonstrated that the yield of 1-butyl oleate increased when the amount of *Rhizopus oryzae* was increased from 30 to 60U and remained almost constant with increase in lipase amount beyond 60U (Ghamuia *et al.*, 2004). Similar results were reported for the methanolysis of rice brain oil catalyzed by *Cryptococcus* Spp. S-2 lipase (Kamini *et al.*, 2001). This may be due to the fact that in the presence of a high amount of lipase, the active site can not be exposed to the substrates and many molecules of the enzyme aggregate together. Agglomeration using immobilized lipase in a solvent-free system has been previously reported (Liou *et al.*, 1998; Foresti and Ferreira, 2005).

A common thread in all studies of enzymes in organic media is that the amount of water associated with the enzyme is a key determinant of the properties (for e.g. activity, stability and specificity) that the enzyme exhibits. It was observed that the percentage conversion was a maximum when no additional water in the reaction mixture. Since the enzyme taken for study already contain water at minimum level, the effect of solvent in the reaction mixture has not been studied and the result does not show any remarkable difference in both free and immobilized system. Although water is necessary for acquisition in essentially anhydrous organic solvents, water is also involved in many enzyme inactivation processes (Volkin *et al.*, 1991). As long as a minimal amount of water is associated with the enzymes, its activity in the organic media is retained. However, too much water facilitates enzyme aggregation, which leads to a decrease in enzyme activity (Iso *et al.*, 2001; Nelson *et al.*, 1996).

Transesterification by using Immobilized Enzymes from different sources

The repeated use of immobilized enzyme may help to bring down the product cost and make the enzymatic process economically viable (Ye *et al.*, 2006). Operational stability or reusability is of importance in determining immobilized enzyme efficiency. However, it was observed that reaction behavior changes when an immobilized enzyme is used repeatedly. This may be due to loss of enzyme during filtration and drying, prolonged interaction of the organic solvent with the immobilized enzyme resulting in the denaturation of the enzyme, and production substantial quantities of co-product water after each cycle (Dave *et al.*, 2006). From the data found in Table-11 and Figure-7 showed that there is not any remarkable difference (in percentage of conversion) in both free and immobilized system but the results obtained from Immobilized system show better in comparison to enzyme in free form.

From this study we found that although the immobilized system does not play a significant role in the process as the comparative result of percentage of conversion in both the cases, but it has been proven to be useful techniques for improving enzyme activity, which is in accordance with the paper (Persson *et al.*, 2002).

CONCLUSION

The present study shows that *Xanthomonas* Spp. shows the best performance followed by the seed of *Jatropha curcas*. From these findings we can try further enhancement of lipase production may be achieved by genetic engineering. High levels of expression of lipases from several micro-organisms have been successfully achieved using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as the host. Accordingly further investigation with these two sources can be taken up for in depth kinetic study before standardizing the protocol without searching for different sources in heat and trial methods. The steps had already been taken by government of India to improve *Jatropha* plants both in increasing seed production and lipase content. It is imperative that investigation must confine with production of bio-diesel from *Jatropha curcas* oil which is non-edible using enzyme from same sources. Preliminary results show a positive energy balance and impact on global warming potential. However more research is needed to get a good insight in the environment sustainability of this production system. It is premature to conclude for sure, the protocol used in this study to be standard as further modification to reduce various steps maximizing ester yield in future

cannot be denied. The high operational stability of immobilized lipase also indicates the efficiency of the process. From the present work, it has been demonstrated that esterification of *jatropha* oil could be effectively carried out in this novel system with a good operational stability of the lipases. However, further research and development on additional fuel property measures, long-term run and wear analysis of biodiesel-filled engines is necessary.

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Table 1 : Lipase contents of different sources in terms of soluble proteins

Enzyme sources	Materials (gms.)	Crude extracts	Enzyme (Conc./ml)	Total content (gms.)
<i>J. curcus</i>	5	2	0.454	0.181
<i>Ricinus</i>	5	2	0.296	0.118
<i>Callophylum</i>	5	2	0.883	0.353
<i>Xanthomonas sp.</i>	5	2	0.338	0.135

Table 2: Measurement of Enzyme activity

Enzyme sources	Wt. of sample (gms)	Vol. of NaOH(ml)	Duration (Min.)	Enzyme activity (Millieq/min/mg)	Activity of gm eq. of material
<i>J. curcus</i>	2	0.3	15	0.001	1
<i>Ricinus</i>	2	0.1	15	0.0003	0.3
<i>Callophylum</i>	2	0.9	15	0.003	3
<i>Xanthomona Sp</i>	2	1.7	15	0.008	8

Table-3: Transesterification by using free enzyme extracted from xanthomonas Sp.

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	8.60	3.2	0.20	86
2	3.0	2	10	8.84	2.95	0.21	88
3	3.5	2	10	8.84	2.96	0.20	88
4	4.0	2	10	8.98	2.70	0.25	89
5	4.5	2	10	9.02	2.74	0.24	90

Table-4: Transesterification by using free enzyme extracted from *Ricinus*

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	7.32	4.47	0.21	73.2
2	3.0	2	10	7.35	4.42	0.23	73.3
3	3.5	2	10	6.96	4.79	0.25	69.6
4	4.0	2	10	7.28	4.46	0.28	72.8
5	4.5	2	10	7.32	4.46	0.22	73.2

Table 5: Transesterification by using free enzyme extracted from *Jatropha curcus*

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	8.21	3.57	0.22	82.00
2	3.0	2	10	8.25	3.50	0.25	82.5
3	3.5	2	10	8.19	3.60	0.21	82.00
4	4.0	2	10	8.26	3.52	0.22	82.60
5	4.5	2	10	8.25	3.51	0.24	82.50

Table 6: Transesterification by using free enzyme extracted from *Callophylum*

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	6.2	5.55	0.25	62
2	3.0	2	10	6.4	5.33	0.27	64
3	3.5	2	10	6.3	5.46	0.24	63
4	4.0	2	10	6.2	5.55	0.25	62
5	4.5	2	10	6.2	5.54	0.26	62

Table-7: Effect of immobilized lipase extracted from seeds of *J. curcus*

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	8.36	3.42	0.22	83.6
2	3.0	2	10	8.74	3.01	0.25	87.4
3	3.5	2	10	8.25	3.54	0.21	82.5
4	4.0	2	10	8.25	3.07	0.22	87.4
5	4.5	2	10	8.34	3.42	0.24	83.4

Table-8: Effect of immobilized lipase extracted from seeds of *Ricinus*

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	7.58	4.21	0.21	75.8
2	3.0	2	10	7.59	4.18	0.23	75.9
3	3.5	2	10	7.01	4.74	0.25	70.1
4	4.0	2	10	7.30	4.44	0.26	73.0
5	4.5	2	10	7.58	4.2	0.22	75.8

Table 9: Effect of immobilized lipase extracted from seeds of *Callophylum*

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	6.4	5.35	0.25	64
2	3.0	2	10	6.8	4.93	0.27	68
3	3.5	2	10	6.5	5.26	0.24	65
4	4.0	2	10	6.4	5.35	0.25	64
5	4.5	2	10	6.3	5.44	0.26	63

Table 10:Effect of immobilized lipase extracted from seeds of bacterial source

Sl. No.	Enzyme (gm.eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil (gm)	Ester (gm)	Other constituents(gm)	Loss (gm)	% of Conversion
1	2.5	2	10	8.87	2.93	0.20	88.7
2	3.0	2	10	8.92	2.87	0.21	89.2
3	3.5	2	10	8.92	2.88	0.20	89.2
4	4.0	2	10	8.99	2.76	0.25	89.9
5	4.5	2	10	9.02	2.73	0.25	90.2

Table 11: Summery of the ester yield in Free and Immobilized enzyme system

Enzyme sources	Enzyme(gm eq. of material)	Ethanol (gm)	Oil(gm)	% of Conversion (Free enzyme)	% of Conversion (Immobilized form)
<i>J. curcus</i>	3	2	10	82.6	87.6
<i>Ricinus</i>	3	2	10	73.5	75.9
<i>Callophylum</i>	3	2	10	64	68
<i>Xanthomonas sp.</i>	4.5	2	10	90	90.2

Figure-1: Lipase content of different sources in terms of soluble protein

Figure-2: Measurement of Enzymatic activity

Figure-3: Enzyme in gm equivalents of material

Figure-4: Enzyme in equivalent of material

Figure-5: Enzyme in gm equivalent of material

Figure-6: Enzyme in gm equivalents of material

Figure-7: Ester yield in Free Enzyme and Immobilized Enzyme

Figure-8: Enzyme in gm equivalents of material

Figure-9: Enzyme in gm equivalents of material

Figure10: Enzyme in gm equivalents of material

Figure-11: Enzyme in gm equivalents of material

Figure-12: Sources of Enzymes

Figure-13: Sources of Enzymes

REFERENCE

- Abigor RD, Uadia PO, Foglia TA, Hass MJ, Jones KC, Okpefa E, Obibuzor JU, Bafor ME. (2000). Lipase-catalyzed production of biodiesel fuel from some Nigerian lauric oils. *Biochem Soc Trans*,28:979-981.
- Belafi Bako K, Kovacs F, Gubicza L, Hancsok J. (2002). Enzymatic biodiesel production from sunflower oil by *Candida antarctica* lipase in a solvent free system. *Biocatal Biotransform*, 20:437-439.
- Crabbe E, Nolasco-Hipolito C, Kobayashi G, Sonomoto K, Ishizaki A. (2001). Biodiesel production from crude palm oil and evaluation of butanol extraction and fuel properties. *Process Biochem*, 37:65-71.
- Dave R, Madamwar D. (2006). Esterification in organic solvents by lipase immobilized in polymer of PVA-alginate-boric acid. *Process Biochem*, 41:951-955.
- Dossat V, Combes D, Marty A. (2002).Lipase-catalyzed transesterification of high oleic sunflower oil. *Enzyme Microbiol Technol*, 30:90-94.
- Dossat V, Combes D, Marty A. (1999). Continuous enzymatic transesterification of high oleic sunflower oil in a packed bed reactor: influence of the glycerol production. *Enzyme Microb Technol*, 25:194-200.
- Du W, Xu YY, Zeng J, Liu DH. (2004). Novozym 435-catalyzed transesterification of crude soya bean oils biodiesel production in a solvent free medium. *Biotechnol Appl Biochem*, 40:187-190.
- Du W, Xu YY, Liu DH, Li ZB. (2005). Study on acyl migration in immobilized liposome TL-catalyzed transesterification of soybean oil. *J Mol Catal B: Enzym* , 37:68-71.
- Du W, Xu YY, Zeng J, Liu DH. (2004). Novozym 435-catalysed transesterification of crude soya bean oils for biodiesel production in a solvent-free medium. *Biotechnol Appl Biochem* 40:187-90.
- Foresti ML, Ferreira ML. (2005). Solvent free ethyl oleate synthesis mediated by lipase from *Candida antarctica* B adsorbed on polypropylene powder. *Cata Today*, 107-108:23-30.
- Francis G, Edinger R, Becker KA. (2005). Concept for simultaneous wasteland reclamation, fuel production, and socio-economic development in degraded areas in India: need, potential and perspective of *Jatropha* plantation. *Nat Resour Forum*, 29:12-24.
- Fukuda H, Kondo A, Noda H. (2001). Biodiesel fuel production by transesterification of oils. *J Biosci Bioeng*, 92:405-416.

- Ghamuia H, Karra Chaabouni M, Gargouri Y. (2004). 1-Butyl oleate synthesis by immobilized lipase from *Rhizopus oryzae*: a comparative study between n-hexane and solvent-free system. *Enzyme Microb Technol*, 35:355-363.
- Hsu AF, Jones K, Foglia TA, Marmer WN. (2002). Immobilized lipase-catalyzed production of alkyl esters of restaurant grease as biodiesel. *Biotechnol Appl Biochem*, 36:181-186.
- Hutner, S. H. (1944). Growth of the photosynthetic bacterium *Rhodospirillum rubrum*. *Arch. Biochem.*, 3, 439-444.
- Iso M, Chen B, Eguchi M, Kudo T, Shrestha S. (2001). Production of biodiesel fuel from triglycerides and alcohol using immobilized lipase. *J Mol Catal Part B: Enzym*, 16:53-58.
- Jaeger KE, Dijkstra BW, Reetz MT. (1999) Bacterial biocatalysts: molecular biology, three-dimensional structures, and biotechnological applications of lipases. *Annu Rev Microbiol*; 53:315–51.
- Jaeger KE, Ransac S, Dijkstra BW, Colson C, Vanheuver M, Misset O. (1994). Bacterial lipase. *FEMS Microbiol Rev*, 15:29–63.
- JP, Lipke N, et al. (2004). Optimization of enzymatic production of biodiesel from castor oil in organic solvent medium. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol*. 113–116:771–80.
- Kaida M, Samukawa T, Kondo A, Fukuda H. (2001). Effect of methanol and water contents on production of biodiesel fuel from plant oil catalyzed by various lipases in a solvent free system. *J Biosci Bioeng*, 91:12-15.
- Kaieda M, Samukawa T, Matsumoto T, Ban K, Kondo A, Shimada Y, Noda H, Nomoto F, Ohtsuka K, Izumoto E, Fukuda H. (1999). Biodiesel fuel production from plant oil catalyzed by *Rhizopus oryzae* lipase in a water containing system without an organic solvent. *J Biosci Bioeng*, 88:627-631.
- Kamini NR, Iefuji H. (2001). Lipase catalyzed methanolysis of vegetable oils in aqueous medium by *Cryptococcus Spp. S-2*. *Process Biochem*, 37:405-410.
- Kusdiana D, Saka S. (2004). Effects of water on biodiesel fuel production by supercritical methanol treatment. *Bioresour Technol*, 91:289-295.
- Li L, Du W, Liu D, Wang L, Li Z. (2006). Lipase-catalyzed transesterification of rapeseed oils for biodiesel production with a novel organic solvent as the reaction medium. *J Mol Catal Part B: Enzyme*, 43:58-62.
- Liou YC, Marangoni AG, Yada RY. (1998). Aggregation behavior of *Candida rugosa* lipase. *Food Res Intern*, 31:243-248.
- National Biodiesel Board. (March 1996). Biodiesel Report.
- Nelson LA, Foglia TA, Marmer WN. (1996). Lipase catalyzed production of biodiesel. *J Am Oil Chem Soc*, 73:1191-1195.
- Noureddini H, Gao X, Philkana RS. (2005). Immobilized *Pseudomonas cepacia* lipase for biodiesel fuel production from soybean oil. *Bioresour Technol*; 96:769–77.
- Ogino H, Miyamoto K, Yasuda M, Ishimi K, and Ishikawa H. (1999). Purification and characterization of organic solvent-stable protease from organic solvent-tolerant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PST-01. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.*, 87, 61-68.
- Oznur K, Tuter M, Aksoy Ha. (2002). Immobilized *Candida Antarctica* lipase-catalyzed alcoholysis of cottonseed oil in a solvent free medium. *Bioresour Technol*, 83:125-129.

- Persson M, Wehtje E, Adlercreutz P. (2002). Factors governing the activity of lyophilized and immobilized lipase preparation in organic solvents. *Chembiochem*, 3:566-571.
- Royon D, Daz M, Ellenrieder G, Locatelli S. (2007). Enzymatic production of biodiesel from cotton seed oil using t-butanol as a solvent. *Bioresour Technol*, 98:648-653.
- Sadasivam S. and Manickam A. (2008). *Biochemical Methods*. New age international publishers. 1-263.
- Samukawa T, kaieda M, Matsumoto T, Ban K, Kondo A, Shimada Y, Noda H, Fukuda H. (2000). Pretreatment of immobilized *Candida antartica* lipase for biodiesel fuel production from plant oil. *J Biosci Bioeng*, 90:180-183.
- Schwab AW, Dykstra GJ, Selke E, Sorenson SC, Pryde EH. (1988). Diesel fuel from thermal decomposition of soybean oil. *J Am Oil Chem Soc*, 65:1781-1786.
- Shah S, Sharma S, Gupta MN. (2004). Biodiesel preparation by lipase-catalyzed transesterification of *Jatropha* oil. *Energy Fuels*, 18:154-159.
- Shah S, Gupta MN. (2007). Lipase catalyzed preparation of biodiesel from *Jatropha* oil in a solvent free system. *Process Biochem*, 42:409-414.
- Shimada Y, Watanabe Y, Sugihara A, Tominaga Y. (2002). Enzymatic alcoholysis for biodiesel fuel production and application of the reaction to oil processing. *J Mol Catal B: Enzym*, 17:133-142.
- Shimada Y, Watanabe Y, Samukawa T, Sugihara A, Noda U, Fukuda H, Tominaga Y. (1999). Conversion of vegetable oil to biodiesel using immobilized *Candida antartica* lipase. *Journal of American oil Chemists' Society*, 76(7): 789-793.
- Shimada Y, Sugihara A, Nagao Y, Tominaga Y. (1992). Induction of *Geotrichum candidum* lipase by long-chain fatty acids. *J Ferment Bioeng*, 74:77-80.
- Shimada Y, Koga C, Sugihara A, Nagao T, Takada N, Tsunasawa S, and Tominaga Y. (1993). Purification and characterization of a novel solvent-tolerant lipase from *Fusarium heterosporum*. *J. Ferment. Bioeng.*, 75, 349-352.
- Sugihara A, Ueshima M, Shimada Y, Tsunasawa S, and Tominaga Y. (1991). Purification and characterization of a novel thermostable lipase from *Pseudomonas cepacia*. *J. Biochem.*, 112, 598-603.
- Volkin DB, Staubli A, Langer R, Klibanov AM. (1991) Enzyme thermo inactivation in anhydrous organic solvents. *Biotechnol Bioeng*, 37:843-853.
- Warabi Y, Kusdiana D, Saka S. (2004). Reactivity of triglycerides and fatty acids of rapeseed oil supercritical alcohols. *Bioresour Technol*, 91:283-287.
- Watanabe Y, Shimada Y, Sugihara A, Noda H, Fukuda H, Tominaga Y. (2000). Continuous production of biodiesel fuel from vegetable oil using immobilized *Candida antarctica*. *J Am Oil Chem*, 77:355-360.
- Ye P, Xu ZK, Wu J, Innocent C, Seta P. (2006). Nanofibrous poly (acrylonitrile-co-maleic acid) membranes functionalized with gelatin and chitosan for lipase immobilization. *Biomaterials*, 27:4169-4176.
- Zhang Y, Dube MA, McLean DD, Kates M. (2003). Biodiesel production from waste cooking oil.1. Process design and technological assessment. *Bioresour Technol*, 89:1-16.

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Correspondence Author

R. K. Sahu

B.J.B Autonomous College, Bhubaneswar, Orissa

sahurajani@yahoo.co.in